

EFFECTIVENESS OF TRANSVAGINAL ULTRASOUND IN DIAGNOSIS OF ECTOPIC PREGNANCY

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Keywords. Ectopic pregnancy, transvaginal ultrasound, diagnostic efficacy.

Background. Ectopic pregnancy is a severe condition presenting as a major health problem for women of childbearing age.

Objective. To determine the effectiveness of primary transvaginal ultrasound in detecting ectopic pregnancy in women attending an early pregnancy examinations.

Materials and methods. This was a prospective observational study. Unselected women attending a specialised EPS unit underwent TVS. Women were categorised as intrauterine pregnancy (IUP), ectopic pregnancy or pregnancy of unknown location (PUL). Women with PUL were monitored until the final determination of the pregnancy site. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV) and negative predictive value with 95% confidence intervals (CI) for primary TVU for diagnosis of ectopic pregnancy were calculated.

Results. During 3 years of the study, 658 women consecutively attended 1st Clinic of Samarkand State Medical Institute.. Outcome data were available for 532 (80.8%) women. In 428 (80.5%) of these cases, the primary TVU showed the presence of a urinary tract infection and in 28 (5.3%) cases, an ectopic pregnancy. The remaining 76 women (14.3%) were classified as PUL and 18 of them (4.2%) were later found to have an ectopic pregnancy. The overall sensitivity of TVU in diagnosing ectopic pregnancy was 77.6% (95% CI: 57.1-89.6) with a specificity of 97.4% (95% CI: 81.2-100), a PPV of 94.3% (95% CI: 85.6-99.8) and an NPV of 97.1% (95% CI: 90.1-99.9).

Conclusions. In unselected women attending a pregnancy centres, the location of the pregnancy can be accurately diagnosed using a single test in more than 90% of all pregnancies and in 77.6 % of ectopic pregnancies.

References:

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